

Full Length Research Paper

Ethical leadership and job performance of teachers in secondary schools in Kyabugimbi Sub-County in Bushenyi District in Southwestern Uganda

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This study sought to establish the relationship between ethical leadership and job performance of teachers in secondary schools in Kyabugimbi Sub-County in Bushenyi District in southwestern Uganda. The study examined the relationship between ethical guidance, power sharing, integrity, fairness, role clarification, and people orientation. The correlational study covered a sample of 124 teachers. Data were collected using a questionnaire survey. Descriptive results revealed that the level of job performance of teachers was good as was head teachers provision of ethical guidance, power sharing, integrity, fairness, role clarification and people orientation. Regression analysis revealed that ethical guidance, power sharing, integrity, fairness, role clarification, and people orientation had a positive and significant influence on job performance of teachers. It was concluded that there was

improvement in job performance of teachers in terms of classroom teaching, management of students, discipline and regularity and interpersonal relations. Further, ethical leadership in terms of ethical guidance, power sharing, integrity, fairness, role clarification, and people orientation are imperative for the performance of secondary schools teachers. It was recommended that in their management of secondary schools, head teachers should offer ethical guidance to teachers, ensure that there is power sharing, maintain high self-integrity, be fair in handling teachers, offer role clarification, and be oriented to their teachers.

Keywords: Ethical leadership, ethical guidance, fairness, integrity, job performance, people orientation, power sharing, role clarification

INTRODUCTION

Parents, education practitioners and policymakers concur that the key to improving education is having highly skilled and effectively performing teachers in all classrooms (Darling-Hammond, 2010). Effective teachers enable students to develop attitudes and behaviours that are important for success in life. Teachers develop students learning self-efficacy, happiness and behaviour (Blazar, and Kraft, 2017). However, despite the importance of performance of teachers, there is a global trend in decline in the job performance of teachers

especially in public schools. For instance, in the western world countries where teachers traditionally showed commitment to performance, today there are also reports about decline in their performance (Shahsavari-Googhari, 2017). For example, since the early 2000s, the education policies of the USA have aimed at identifying and punishing individual teachers due students' poor achievement, creating a culture that blames and shames teachers (Symeonidis, 2015). According to Ozoemena, (2013), in many countries especially in the developing

world of Africa, the challenge of decline in the job performance of teachers is even higher with teachers not attending to students. In Uganda, performance of teachers is not any better than other countries in Africa. Teachers show lack of motivation to carry out their job of teaching (Nakabugo, Byamugisha and Bithaghalire, 2008). About 15 percent of teachers do not turn up to teach their classes (Oduut, 2017). Teachers also report late and not execute all their professional duties like making schemes of work, lesson plans and performing weekly duty (Musoke, 2016). Komakech and Osuu, (2014) reveal that over the years, poor performance of teachers is reflected in the dismal performance of students in Uganda National Examinations Board. Due to the importance of performance of teachers, a number of studies (Bryson, Stokes and Wilkinson, 2017; Dee and Wyckoff, 2015; Garet et al., 2017; Hervie and Winful, 2018; Imhangbe, Okecha and Obozuwa, 2018; Malik, Awais, Timsal and Qureshi, 2016; Shulhan, 2018) have been devoted to examining factors affecting it. The studies above suggest that factors relating to performance of teacher included human resource management practices, principals' leadership styles and ethical leadership. However, while all the other factors were examined in the context of secondary schools, ethical leadership was studied in the context of a university. This study therefore found it imperative to examine the relationship between ethical leadership and performance of teachers in the context of secondary schools.

Performance of teachers

Performance is the record of results when employees have carried out a job for a certain period or the effectiveness of goals that have been achieved (Hsiung, 2014). Therefore, job performance is the ability (both physical and psychological) to perform a particular task in a specific method that can be evaluated as excellent, average or low on a scale (Raza, Anjum and Zia, 2014). Performance is the result of work that can be achieved by a person or group of people in an organisation, in accordance with the authority and responsibilities of each, in an effort to achieve the goals of the organisation (Gewasari, Manullang and Sibuea, 2017). Therefore, job performance of teachers refers to the ability of teachers to combine relevant inputs for the enhancement of teaching and learning processes (Amin, ullah Shah, Ayaz and Atta, 2013). Job performance of teachers is about designing lessons, providing instruction based on those lessons, and designing and implementing classroom management strategies to maximise the efficacy of instructional lessons within a classroom's environment (Steinberg and Garrett, 2016). Hanif and Pervez, (2004) conceptualised job performance of teachers as a multi-dimensional concept covering classroom teaching, management, discipline and regularity, and interpersonal

relations performance. Basing on the five identified dimensions of job performance of teachers, this study assessed the performance teachers and measured whether the items defining the same were valid and reliable measures.

Ethical leadership

Ethical leadership is the demonstration of normatively appropriate conduct through personal actions and interpersonal relationships, and the promotion of such conduct to followers through two-way communication, reinforcement and decision-making (Phillips and Gully, 2013). Ethical leaders use their social power in their decisions, their own actions, and their influence on others in such a way that they act in the best interest of followers and not enact harm upon them by respecting the rights of all parties (Stouten, van Dijke and De Cremer, 2012). Ethical leaders that demonstrate the highest moral standards and ethical conduct in their everyday talk, actions, decisions and behaviours make those under them in the organisation to follow suit (Toor and Ofori, 2009). Kalshoven, Den Hartog and De Hoogh, (2011) dimensionalised ethical leadership as including ethical guidance, power sharing, integrity, fairness, role clarification, and people orientation. This study examined the relationship between the ethical leadership dimensions and job performance of teachers.

Theoretical review

Leader-Member Exchange (LMX) Theory by Graen and Uhl-Bien, (1995) underpins the relationship between ethical leadership and employee job performance. LMX proposes that supervisors establish relationships with subordinates that range on a continuum from lower to higher quality exchanges. Low LMX relationships are mainly based on economic exchange between the employer and employee (time is exchanged for money) (Tummers and Bronkhorst, 2014). High-quality LMX relationships represent commitment to one another, a willingness to support one another, and confidence in the other's loyalty (Martin, Epitropaki, Thomas and Topakas, 2010). When the supervisor and subordinate share a high-quality LMX relationship experience, the leader is likely to provide outcomes desired by subordinates, such as interesting tasks, additional responsibilities, and larger rewards and the subordinates reciprocate with commitment to work and loyalty to the leader (Mugizi, Bakkabulindi and Bisaso, 2015). A high-quality relationship between supervisors and employees is crucial for performance at work (Volmer, Niessen, Spurk, Linz and Abele, 2011). In this study, it was assumed that ethical leadership in terms of fairness, power sharing, role clarification, and people oriented behaviour, integrity and ethical guidance is a high exchange relationship and

this thus relates job performance.

Ethical guidance and job performance

Ethical guidance pertains to the leader's communication about ethics, explanation of ethical rules, and promotion and reward of ethical conduct among subordinates (Kalshoven et al., 2011). With ethical guidance, the leader clearly explains integrity-related codes of conduct, integrity behaviours expected from employees, provides integrity guidelines, ensures that employees follow codes of integrity and clarifies the likely consequences of possible unethical behaviour (Men, 2015). However, Khalid and Bano, (2015) in analysis of the relationship between supervisor's ethical guidance and employee task initiatives established that the relationship was insignificant. Nonetheless, Saeed, Shakeel and Lodhi, (2013) ethical guidance had a positive and significant on employee performance. However, as the literature above suggested, studies on ethical guidance were limited. This gap made it necessary for this empirical study to further investigate whether the hypothesis to the effect that: H1: Integrity influences job performance of teachers.

Power sharing and job performance

Power sharing is the process of sharing responsibility for decision making and actions among stakeholders in collaboration promoting different participants' influences (Ran and Qi, 2018). Power sharing can be manifested in various acts such sharing leadership, resources, rewards, and outcomes; encouraging participation in decision making, and delegation of authority (Coleman, 2004). Power sharing empowers subordinates by providing them more discretion in performing their tasks, more confidence to think and act as organisational partners and work creatively (Chen, Zhang and Wang, 2014). In their study, Arslan and Zaman, (2014) found out that empowerment had a positive significant effect on job performance. Chen and Aryee, (2007) reported a positive significant relationship between delegation and employee task performance. Similarly, Chen et al. (2014) established that power sharing improved job performance. In a meta-analysis, Gonzalez, (2010) established that workers direct participation led to increases in labour productivity. Khalid and Bano, (2015) revealed that power sharing had a positive and significant relationship with individual's task initiatives. However, the contexts of the study were outside the developing of Africa making it necessary for this study in the context of a developing country in Africa to establish if the following hypothesis held: H2: Fairness influences job performance of teachers.

Integrity and job performance

Integrity is conduct that depicts consistency of actions, values, methods, measures, principles, expectations and

outcomes that suggests a deep commitment to doing the right thing for the right reason, regardless of the circumstances (Sani et al., 2016). Integrity is the state of being morally trustworthy, honest, fully integrated and whole, true to oneself, and/or acting in accordance with one's statements (Bauman, 2013). Integrity reflects the ability of the individual in performing assigned tasks (Sani et al., 2016). Leadership integrity is a perceived driver of follower performance behaviours because of trust in the leader (Leroy, Palanski and Simons, 2012). An empirical analysis by Djail, Indriani and Dariyansah, (2016) revealed that leadership integrity had a significant effect on the performance of employees. Leroy et al. (2012) found out that leader behavioural integrity was related to follower work role performance. Luther, (2000) established that integrity was related to transformed performance ratings within a high performance team environment. Conversely, Palanski and Yammarino, (2011) reported that leader behavioural integrity was not directly related to follower job performance. However, Sani et al. (2016) revealed that integrity was important for improving job performance. White and Lean, (2008) found out that perceived leader integrity had a positive impact on activities of employees. However, all the studies were skewed outside the developing context of Africa. Thus, it was deemed crucial for this study to test whether: H3: Integrity influences job performance of teachers.

Fairness and job performance

Fairness refers to the judgment by individuals of whether an outcome and/ or the process to reach an outcome are reasonable, acceptable, or just (Xia, Monroe and Cox, 2004). Fairness is when an individual feels he or she has been treated justly. Fairness invokes the principle that people are treated according to their rights (Goldman and Cropanzano, 2015). Fairness of treatment received from authorities has an important influence on people's attitudes and behaviour such as good work performance (van Knippenberg, De Cremer and van Knippenberg, 2007). In their study, Collins, Mossholder and Taylor (2012) found out that fairness had a positive significant influence on employee performance. However, Khalid and Bano, (2015) reported that supervisor's fairness had an insignificant relationship with individual's task initiatives. Nevertheless, Selvarajan, Singh and Solansky, (2018) revealed that all dimensions of fairness positively related to performance of employees. Similarly, Sugianingrat, Yasa, Sintaasih and Subudi, (2017) established that fairness had not direct influence on employee performance. Wu, Sturman and Wang, (2013) indicated that overall, fairness was a positive significant predictor of employees' job performance. However, while all the other scholars reported positive significant relationships between fairness and employee performance, Khalid and Bano, (2015) and Sugianingrat

et al. (2017) did not. This empirical gap made it necessary for this study to test the hypothesis to the effect that: H4: Fairness influences job performance of teachers.

Role clarification and job performance

Role clarification is the degree to which required information is provided about how the employee is expected to perform his or her job (Lynn and Kalay, 2016). With role clarification, there is clarifying of expectations and communicating openly so that followers understand what is desired and expected of them (Katuramu, Byarugaba and Mugizi, 2016). Role clarification leads to role clarity which is important for better individual job outcomes (Lynn and Kalay, 2016). In an empirical study, Celik, (2013) revealed that the indirect and direct effects of role ambiguity on job performance were significant. Lynn and Kalay, (2016) found out that role clarity was not significantly related to team performance. Samie, Riahi and Tabibi, (2015) reported that there was a positive significant relationship between role clarity and general efficiency of the employees. Thangavelu and Sudhahar, (2017) reported existence of a significant correlation between role clarity and employee job performance. However, while all the other scholars found a positive and significant relationship between role clarity and job performance, Celik, (2013) and Lynn and Kalay (2016) did not. These controversial results suggested an empirical gap. This made it essential for this study to further test the correctness of the following hypothesis: H5: Role clarification influences job performance of teachers.

People oriented behaviour and job performance

People orientation is about a leader behaving in a way that shows real concern for people by expressing genuine care, respect and support for the followers to ensure that their aspirations are fulfilled (Khalid and Bano, 2015). People oriented leaders prioritise the welfare of every single employee, and do not hesitate to spend time and effort in meeting their individual needs (Ruzgar 2018). People oriented leaders enhance member skills and leader member relationship leading to commitment to the mission of the organization (Yukl, 2012.) In their study, Fayyaz, Naheed and Hasan, (2014) reported a strong positive and significant association between relational leadership styles and employee performance. Fernandez, (2008) found out that relationship-oriented behaviour had a positively statistically significant relationship with perceived work unit performance. Guo, Dai and Yang, (2016) revealed that the relationship between leadership relational behaviour and job performance was insignificant. Taberner, Chambel,

Curral and Arana, (2009) established that relationship-oriented leaders generated greater cohesion between members of the group hence high group job performance. However, whereas all the other studies suggested a significant relationship between people oriented behaviour and job performance, Guo et al. (2016) did not. This contradiction made it necessary for this study to further examine whether: H6: People oriented behaviour influences job performance of teachers.

METHODOLOGY

Sample and procedure

The sample comprised 127 respondents in both government aided and private secondary schools in Kyabugimbi Sub-County in Bushenyi District in southwestern Uganda. The correlational study adopted a questionnaire survey that was completed by subject teachers, class teachers and head of departments. The selection of the aforementioned respondents was based on the assumption that they could provide their perceptions on the ethical leadership of the head teachers because they experienced it since they were active teachers in the schools. The study employed simple random sampling by which the respondents were selected at random and entirely by chance. This enabled collection of data from a representative sample. The researchers personally collected and remained ethical throughout the whole study. The researchers obtained informed consent, ensured anonymity, confidentiality, respect for privacy and honesty in the reporting of data.

Instrument

Using the quantitative paradigm and in particular the survey design, data were collected using a self-administered questionnaire (SAQ). The question items in section A were nominal questions on background characteristics. Section B and C question items were ordinal questions on the dependent variable (performance of teachers) and independent variable (ethical leadership). The items on job performance of teachers covered four aspects, namely teaching, management, discipline and regularity and interpersonal relations performance (25 items = 7, 5, 6 and 7 items respectively with overall $\alpha = 0.81$) (Amin, ullah Shah, Ayaz and Atta, 2013). The items on ethical leadership covered its six dimensions. These were namely; fairness (5 items, $\alpha = 0.87$), power sharing (6 items, $\alpha = 0.84$), role clarification (5 items, $\alpha = 0.86$), people orientation (6 items, $\alpha = 0.90$), integrity (4 items $\alpha = 0.94$) and ethical guidance (6 items $\alpha = 0.94$) (Kalshoven et al., 2011). The questions in sections B and C were scaled using the five-

point Likert scale from a minimum of 1 for the worst case scenario (strongly disagree) to a maximum of 5 which is the best case scenario (Strongly agree).

Data management and analysis

The data were processed by coding all the questionnaires, entering the data into the computer using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS), summarising them using frequency tables and editing them to remove errors. Quantitative research methods were used to establish the validity and reliability of the data collection questionnaire. The validities of the items on each construct were tested using Factor Analysis. Reliability tests for the constructs were done using Cronbach's Alpha (α). Data analysis involved descriptive, correlation and regression analyses. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) was used in carrying out analysis of data.

RESULTS

Demographic characteristics

The results in Table 1 on background characteristics of the participants revealed that typical respondents (55.1%) were male, aged up to 29 years (52.8%), possessed bachelor degrees (49.6%), with experience of less than 5 years (62.2%), and were subject teachers 58.3%.

Job performance of teachers

Job performance of teachers was operationalized as a multi-dimensional concept covering classroom teaching, management of students, discipline and regularity and interpersonal relations. The results on job performance of teachers include frequencies, percentages, and means. Validity and reliability test that are factor loadings and Cronbach's alpha (α) are also presented. These indicate the accuracy and interrelatedness of the items measuring the different aspects of job performance teachers. The results on job performance of teachers were as presented in (Table 2).

Table 2 shows that teachers rated their performance as good (classroom teaching overall mean = 4.26, management of students = 4.23, discipline and regularity = 4.38 and interpersonal relations = 4.33 all corresponding to agreed). Factor Analysis indicated that the items for each of the four components of job performance of teachers could be reduced to only one factor, with the factors having eigenvalues of 2.868, 2.530, 2.724 and 3.826 respectively. The factors explained over 40%, 50%, 45% and 54% respectively of the joint variation in the respective items constituting a

factor. Since a factor loading of at least 0.5 is considered strong (Pedrosa, Rodrigues, Padilha, Gallani and Alexandre, 2016), Table 2 suggests that each item loaded highly on the corresponding factor hence valid measures of the respective constructs. The Cronbach's alphas = 0.738, 0.745, 0.741 and 0.712 for the respective components of job performance of teachers were above the acceptable level = 0.70 (Taber, 2018). This implied that the items for the four components of job performance of teachers were reliable measures.

Ethical leadership

Ethical leadership was measured using six constructs namely; ethical guidance, power sharing, integrity, fairness, role clarification and people orientation. The results on ethical leadership included frequencies, percentages and means. For each construct of ethical leadership, factor loadings and Cronbach's alpha (α) results are presented showing the validity and reliability of the results. The results on ethical leadership constructs are as presented in (Table 3). Table 3 shows that teachers rated ethical guidance by head teachers (overall mean of ethical guidance (EC) = 4.26, power sharing (PS) = 4.12, integrity (I) = 4.16, fairness (F) = 4.40, role clarification (RC) = 4.16 and people orientation (PO) = 3.61 all corresponding to agreed) as being good. Factor Analysis indicated that the items for each of the six components of ethical guidance could be reduced to only one factor, with the factors having eigen values of 3.639, 2.588, 2.241, 3.425, 2.507 and 3.497 respectively. The factors explained over 60%, 43%, 56%, 68%, 50% and 58% respectively of the joint variation in the respective items constituting a factor. Since a factor loading of at least 0.5 is considered strong, Table 2 suggests that each item loaded highly on the corresponding factor. Therefore, all the items were valid measures of the respective constructs (ethical guidance, power sharing, integrity, fairness, role clarification and people orientation). The Cronbach's alphas = 0.740, 0.719, 0.712, 0.702, 0.730 and 0.854 for the respective components of job performance of teachers were above the acceptable level = 0.70. This suggests that the items for the six components of ethical leadership of head teachers were reliable measures.

Ethical leadership and job performance of teachers

To establish whether there was an association between ethical leadership components namely; ethical guidance, power sharing, integrity, fairness, role clarification, and people orientation and job performance of teachers, a regression analysis was carried out (Table 4). Table 4 shows that the components of ethical leadership namely; ethical guidance, power sharing, integrity, fairness, role

Table 1. Background characteristics.

Item	Categories	Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	70	55.1
	Female	57	44.9
	Total	127	100.0
Age groups	Up to 29 years	67	52.8
	30-39 years	34	26.8
	30-39 years	23	18.1
	50 years and above	3	2.4
	Total	127	100.0
Education levels	Diploma	60	47.2
	Bachelor's degree	63	49.6
	Post graduate qualifications	4	3.1
	Total	127	100.0
Experience	Less than 5 years	79	62.2
	5 - 10 years	43	33.9
	11 years and above	5	3.9
	Total	127	100.0
Responsibility	Subject teacher	74	58.3
	Class teacher	23	18.1
	Head of department	29	22.8
	Senior administrator	1	0.8
	Total	127	100.0

Table 2. Means, factors loadings and cronbach's alphas for job performance of teachers.

CT	Overall Mean = 4.26	Mean	Factor loadings	α
CT1		4.38	0.638	0.738
CT2		4.38	0.753	
CT3		3.69	0.687	
CT4		4.43	0.581	
CT5		3.74	0.489	
CT6		4.45	0.658	
CT7		4.71	0.643	
EFA			Eigen value (2.868)	% of Variance (40.978)
MS	Overall Mean = 4.23	Mean	Factor loadings	α
MS1		4.09	0.727	0.745
MS2		4.08	0.577	
MS3		4.12	0.827	
MS4		4.61	0.644	
MS5		4.27	0.756	
EFA			Eigen value (2.530)	
DR	Overall Mean = 4.38	Mean	Factor loadings	α
DR1		3.92	0.636	0.741
DR2		4.68	0.629	
DR3		4.35	0.677	
DR4		4.41	0.693	
DR5		4.20	0.714	
DR6		4.75	0.691	
EFA			Eigen value (2.724)	
IR	Overall Mean =4.33	Mean	Factor loadings	α
IR1		4.18	0.603	0.712
IR2		4.38	0.692	
IR3		4.47	0.709	
IR4		4.43	0.510	
IR5		4.40	0.723	
IR6		4.20	0.711	
IR7		4.26	0.681	
EFA			Eigen value (3.826)	

Table 3. Means, factors loadings and cronbach's alphas for job performance of teachers.

EG	Overall Mean = 4.26	Mean	Factor loadings	α
EG1		4.14	0.711	0.740
EG2		4.37	0.714	
EG3		4.41	0.669	
EG4		4.38	0.549	
EG5		4.33	0.599	
EG6		4.17	0.711	
EFA			Eigen value (3.639)	
PS	Overall mean = 4.12	Mean	Factor loadings	α
PS1		4.27	0.679	0.719
PS2		4.36	0.765	
PS3		3.72	0.645	
PS4		4.38	0.633	
PS5		3.62	0.527	
PS6		4.35	0.669	
EFA			Eigen value (2.588)	
I	Overall Mean =4.16	Mean	Factor loadings	α
I1		4.20	0.758	0.712
I2		4.31	0.813	
I3		4.31	0.741	
I4		3.81	0.675	
EFA			Eigen value (2.241)	
F	Overall Mean =4.40	Mean	Factor loadings	α
F 1		4.25	0.737	0.702
F 2		4.19	0.690	
F 3		4.44	0.705	
F 4		4.57	0.696	
F 5		4.52	0.756	
EFA			Eigen value (3.425)	% of Variance (68.502)
RC	Overall Mean =4.16	Mean	Factor loadings	α
RC1		4.15	0.661	0.730
RC2		4.24	0.701	
RC3		4.29	0.809	
RC4		4.28	0.719	
RC5		3.80	0.637	
EFA			Eigen value (2.507)	% of Variance (50.139)
PO	Overall Mean =3.61	Mean	Factor loadings	α
PO1		3.34	0.759	0.854
PO2		3.54	0.819	
PO3		3.78	0.663	
PO4		3.73	0.774	
PO5		3.53	0.816	
PO6		3.37	0.739	
EFA			Eigen value (3.497)	

clarification, and people orientation explained 67.3% of the variation in job performance of teachers (adjusted $R^2 = 0.673$). This means that 32.7% of the variation was accounted for by other factors not considered under this model. All the components of ethical leadership, namely; ethical guidance ($\beta = 0.194$, $p = 0.001 < 0.05$), power sharing ($\beta = 0.587$, $p = 0.000 < 0.05$), integrity ($\beta = 0.595$, $p = 0.002 < 0.05$), fairness ($\beta = 0.241$, $p = 0.000 < 0.05$),

role clarification ($\beta = 0.758$, $p = 0.000 < 0.05$), and people orientation ($\beta = 0.208$, $p = 0.001 < 0.05$) had a positive and significant influence on job performance of teachers. This means that all the hypotheses (H_1 - H_5) were supported. The magnitudes of the respective betas suggested that role clarification had the most significant influence on job performance of teachers followed integrity, power sharing, fairness, people orientation and

Table 4. Regression of job performance of teachers on ethical leadership.

Ethical Leadership	Standardised Coefficients	
	Beta (β)	Significance (p)
Ethical guidance	0.194	0.001
Power sharing	0.587	0.000
Integrity	0.595	0.002
Fairness	0.241	0.000
Role clarification	0.758	0.000
People orientation	0.208	0.001
Adjusted R ² = 0.673		
F = 35.995, p = 0.000		

ethical guidance respectively.

DISCUSSION

The results of the study revealed that job performance of teachers in terms of classroom teaching, management of students, discipline and regularity and interpersonal relations was good. This finding was inconsistent with the premise on which this study was based that job performance of teachers was poor. Anecdotal contextual evidence suggested that many teachers failed to execute all their professional duties (Musoke, 2016). However, the findings of this study revealed that this was not true and teachers executed their duties effectively. Therefore, contrary to the initial perception that performance of teachers was poor, it was actually good. The findings of the study also revealed that all aspects of ethical leadership namely ethical guidance, power sharing, integrity, fairness, role clarification, and people orientation had a positive and significant relationship with job performance of teachers. This finding is consistent with the findings of previous scholars. For example, Arslan and Zaman, (2014) reported that empowerment had a positive significant effect on job performance. Chen and Aryee, (2007) revealed a positive significant relationship between delegation and employee task performance. Chen et al. (2014) found out that power sharing improved job performance. Djalil et al. (2016) indicated that leadership integrity had a significant effect on the performance of employees. Gonzalez, (2010) established that direct participation led to increases in labour productivity. Fayyaz et al. (2014) indicated that association between relational leadership styles and employee performance was positive and significant. Fernandez, (2008) reported that relationship between relations-oriented behaviour and work unit performance was positive and significant. Consistent with the findings of the study, Khalid and Bano, (2015) also revealed that supervisor's ethical leadership had a significant positive relationship with an employee's task initiatives. Luther, (2000) indicated that integrity was related to transformed performance ratings. Saeed et al. (2013) reported that ethical guidance had a positive and significant on

employee performance. Samie et al. (2015) found out that there was a positive significant relationship between role clarity and general efficiency of the employees. Sani et al. (2016) agreed that integrity was important for improving job performance. Selvarajan et al. (2018) confirmed that fairness positively related to performance employees. Thangavelu and Sudahar, (2017) revealed that there was a significant correlation between role clarity and employee job performance. Taberero et al. (2009) ascertained that relationship-oriented leaders generated greater cohesion between members of the group hence high group job performance. Similarly, White and Lean, (2008) reported that perceived leader integrity had an impact on activities of employees. However, the finding that all ethical leadership aspects had a positive and significant relationship with job performance was inconsistent with the findings of some scholars. For example, Guo et al. (2016) found out that the relationship between leadership relational behaviour and job performance was insignificant. Lynn and Kalay, (2016) revealed that role clarity was not significantly related to team performance. Palanski and Yammarino, (2011) indicated that leader behavioural integrity was not directly related to follower job performance as was Sugianingrat et al. (2017) who reported that fairness had not direct influence on employee performance. Nevertheless, the findings of previous studies consistent with the finding of the current study, it can be deduced that ethical leadership has a positive and significant relationship with job performance of teachers.

Conclusion

The discussion above suggests that job performance of teachers in terms of classroom teaching, management of students, discipline and regularity and interpersonal relations in secondary schools in Uganda had improved. This is because contextual anecdotal evidence suggested it was poor with teachers not attending to their students but concentrating on their private businesses, reporting late to schools and failing to execute all their professional duties. Also, from the discussion it can also be deduced that ethical leadership in terms of ethical

guidance, power sharing, integrity, fairness, role clarification, and people orientation are imperative for the performance of secondary schools teachers. Therefore, it is recommended that in their management of secondary schools, head teachers should offer ethical guidance to teachers, ensure that there is power sharing, maintain high self-integrity, be fair in handling teachers, offer role clarification, and be oriented to their teachers. This will make teachers put in improved job performance. Nevertheless, the findings of the study were limited to one sub country in a district in south-western Uganda. Future research should extend the study to a wider geographical scope in Uganda and even beyond.

Authors' declaration

We declared that this study is an original research by our research team and we agree to publish it in the journal.

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Appendix. Study instrument

Construct	Item	Measures
Section A: Background Characteristics		
	BV1	BV2 Gender (Male, Female)
	BV2	Age groups in years (Up to 29 years; 30-39 years; 30-39 years; 50 years and above)
	BV3	Highest level of education attained by the respondent (Bachelor's degree; Postgraduate diploma; Master's degree; PhD degree)
	BV4	Experience (Less than 5 years, 5 - 10 years, 11 years and above)
	BV5	Responsibility (Subject teacher; Class teacher; Head of department Senior administrator)
Section B: Job Performance of Teachers		
		Measures
Classroom Teaching (CT)	CT1	I use different methods of teaching
	CT2	I ensure that most of my students understand my lessons
	CT3	I teach every student according to his abilities
	CT4	I come well prepared for teaching in class
	CT5	I can also teach difficult lessons easily
	CT6	I make effort to satisfy student when they asks question
	CT7	I carry out management responsibilities effectively
Management of students (MS)	MS1	I involve students in co- curricular activities
	MS2	I fulfill my duties of directing students
	MS3	I accept responsibilities offered to me by my supervisors
	MS4	I try to improve the performance of students
	MS5	I carry out management responsibilities effectively
Discipline and regularity (DR)	DR1	I ensure students come to school regularly
	DR2	When present at school I attend to my class on time
	DR3	I do relevant activities in my periods that regulate students
	DR4	I fulfill my assigned activities that maintain discipline
	DR5	I ensure the students fulfill curriculum requirements
	DR6	I maintain discipline in my class
Interpersonal relations (IR)	IR1	I try to solve problems that arise between me and colleagues
	IR2	I enjoy good relations with my colleagues
	IR3	I co-operate with my colleagues in any work
	IR4	I consult my colleagues in solving of my class problems
	IR5	I keep good relations with my students
	IR6	I try to be in touch with parents of my students
	IR7	I make effort to maintain good relations in the school
Section C: Ethical Leadership		
		Measures
	EG1	My head teacher clarifies the likely consequences of possible unethical behaviour by colleagues and myself.
	EG2	My head teacher in this school stimulates the discussion of integrity issues among staff
	EG3	My head teacher in this school ensures that I follow codes of integrity
	EG4	My head teacher in this school clearly explains integrity related codes of conduct

Appendix Contd.. Study instrument

	EG5	My head teacher in this school clarifies integrity guidelines
	EG6	My head teacher in this school explains what is expected from staff in terms of behaving with integrity
Power sharing (PS)	PS1	My head teacher in this school allows subordinates to influence critical decisions
	PS2	My head teacher in this school allow others to participate in decision making
	PS3	My head teacher in this school seeks advice from subordinates concerning organizational strategy
	PS4	My head teacher in this school reconsiders decisions on the basis of recommendations by those who report to them
	PS5	I am delegated challenging responsibilities in this school by my head teacher
	PS6	In this school I am permitted to play a key role in setting my performance goals
Integrity (I)	I1	I trust that my head teacher in this school to do the things he/ she says
	I2	My head teacher in this school always keeps his words
	I3	My head teacher in this school keeps his/ her promises
	I4	My head teacher in this school can be relied on to honour his commitments
Fairness (F)	F 1	My head teacher in this school pursues the success of all staff
	F 2	My head teacher in this focuses mainly on reaching the goals of all staff
	F 3	I am held responsible for things that are my fault in this school by my head teacher
	F 4	My head teacher holds me responsible for work that I have control over in this school
	F 5	My head teacher in this school holds me accountable for problems over which I have control
Role Clarification	RC1	My head teacher in this school indicates what the performance expectations of each group member are
	RC2	My head teacher in this school explains what is expected of each group member
	RC3	My head teacher in this school explain what is expected of me and my colleagues
	RC4	My head teacher in this school clarifies priorities
	RC5	My head teacher in this school clarifies who is responsible for what
People Orientation (PO)	PO1	My head teacher in this school is genuinely concerned about my personal development
	PO2	My head teacher in this school takes time to talk about work-related emotions
	PO3	My head teacher in this school pays attention to my personal needs
	PO4	My head teacher in this school takes time for personal contact
	PO5	My head teacher sympathises with me when I have problems
	PO6	My head teacher in this school is interested in how I feel and how I am doing